

Fifth Order Inverse Vibrational Problems by the Method of Isotani

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Force constants of HNCS and DNCS involving fifth order vibrational problems have been calculated by a new technique of solving the secular equation $|GF - \lambda E| = 0$, after substituting for all the off-diagonal elements F_{ij} from Isotani's formula. The new technique consists of determining the values of the functions and the derivatives involved by utilising the symmetry in the equations. The force constants determined are compared with those obtained by other methods.

GENERALLY force constants are evaluated by solving the secular equation $|GF - \lambda E| = 0$. But the inherent difficulty in solving the secular equation is that there are more unknown elements F_{ij} than the number of equations. For an $n \times n$ order problem there are $n(n+1)/2$ unknown force constants and n known fundamental frequencies. To get over this difficulty, one must include $n(n-1)/2$ equations additionally. In some approximation methods¹ constraints are imposed either on the element of F-matrix or on the element of L-matrix so as to obtain the necessary additional equations. We present here the Isotani's method² which involves evaluation of off-diagonal force constants using expressions for them obtained on the basis of experimental force constants of high symmetry molecules.

For a third order problem the off-diagonal element F_{ij} is determined by considering the corresponding i and j modes only and the diagonal values F_{ii} and F_{jj} are obtained later using the secular equation considering only the i and j modes, treating this to be the second order problem. Similar calculations for all F_{ij} leads to two values for each F_{ij} and one set for F_{ii} . These values of F_{ii} appear to be close together and their average value is obtained as an approximate solution.

In an $n \times n$ problem, it is found that the diagonal elements F_{ii} obtained $(n-1)$ times were all consistently close enough to justify the taking of the average. The values of F_{ii} together with the off-diagonal F_{ij} values satisfy the secular equation only approximately. To refine them and satisfy the secular equation the F_{ij} values are fixed as obtained from Isotani's method and substituted into the secular equation to obtain n non-linear equations of varying degrees in n unknown elements F_{ii} . Newton-Raphson's iterative method is applied here to solve for the F_{ii} values. Here the average values of F_{ii} calculated earlier are used as initial set for the iterative procedure.

The iterative method involves mainly the calculation of the values of the functions and their derivatives at the corresponding points. Here a new general procedure is developed to obtain these values of functions and derivatives in a unique way

using the symmetry in the secular equations. This is explained below in a third order problem.

Third order problem :

In the third order problem (3×3) the secular equation $|H - \lambda E| = 0$, leads to the following three equation (where $H = GF$),

$$f_1 = H_{11} + H_{22} + H_{33} - (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3) = 0$$

$$f_2 = \begin{vmatrix} H_{11} & H_{12} \\ H_{21} & H_{22} \end{vmatrix} + \begin{vmatrix} H_{11} & H_{13} \\ H_{31} & H_{33} \end{vmatrix} + \begin{vmatrix} H_{22} & H_{23} \\ H_{32} & H_{33} \end{vmatrix} - (\lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3 + \lambda_3 \lambda_1) = 0$$

$$f_3 = \begin{vmatrix} H_{11} & H_{12} & H_{13} \\ H_{21} & H_{22} & H_{23} \\ H_{31} & H_{32} & H_{33} \end{vmatrix} - \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 = 0$$

where $H_{ij} = G_{ii} F_{ij} + G_{2i} F_{2i} + G_{3i} F_{3i}$.

The derivatives are

$$\frac{\delta f_1}{\delta F_{ii}} = G_{ii} \quad (i=1 \text{ to } 3)$$

$$\frac{\delta f_2}{\delta F_{11}} = \begin{vmatrix} G_{11} & H_{12} \\ G_{12} & H_{22} \end{vmatrix} + \begin{vmatrix} G_{11} & H_{13} \\ G_{13} & H_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\delta f_2}{\delta F_{22}} = \begin{vmatrix} H_{11} & G_{12} \\ H_{21} & G_{22} \end{vmatrix} + \begin{vmatrix} G_{22} & H_{23} \\ G_{23} & H_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\delta f_2}{\delta F_3} = \begin{vmatrix} H_{11} & G_{13} \\ H_{31} & G_{33} \end{vmatrix} + \begin{vmatrix} H_{22} & G_{23} \\ H_{32} & G_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\delta f_3}{\delta F_{11}} = \begin{vmatrix} G_{11} & H_{12} & H_{13} \\ G_{12} & H_{22} & H_{23} \\ G_{13} & H_{32} & H_{33} \end{vmatrix}; \quad \frac{\delta f_3}{\delta F_{22}} = \begin{vmatrix} H_{11} & G_{12} & H_{13} \\ H_{21} & G_{22} & H_{23} \\ H_{31} & G_{23} & H_{33} \end{vmatrix};$$

$$\frac{\delta f_3}{\delta F_{33}} = \begin{vmatrix} H_{11} & H_{12} & G_{13} \\ H_{21} & H_{22} & G_{23} \\ H_{31} & H_{32} & G_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

The general $n \times n$ problem : It may be observed that there is a certain uniformity or similarity in the functions and their derivatives which can be utilised to evaluate their values. The function f_i consists of the difference between the sum of all the principal minors of order i of the matrix-H and a similar sum for a diagonal matrix, Λ having λ_i on their diagonals. The sum of all the principal minors of various orders can be directly obtained from the characteristic equations of the corresponding matrices.

The derivative of f_i with respect to F_{kk} involves the sum of all principal minors of order i involving H_{kk} only, where H' is the matrix obtained by replacing the k th column of matrix-H by the k th column of matrix-G. To obtain the derivative of f_i with respect to F_{kk} , the k th column in matrix-H is replaced by the k th column of matrix-G and the sum of the principal minors of orders i is determined and from this the sum of the principal minors of order i in a truncated matrix-H (leaving out the k th row and k th column) is subtracted.

The advantage of this general procedure is that it can be applied directly to a general n th order problem and there is no limitation on its extension to a general $n \times n$ case.

Results and Discussion

The technique described in the previous section is applied to two molecules, HNCS and DNCS involving fifth order vibrational problem. The molecules HNCS and DNCS belong to the C_s point group having six distinct normal modes of vibration, which fall under the irreducible representation $5A' + A''$. The A'' vibrational mode is an out-of-plane bending one. All the vibrations are active in infrared and Raman spectra.

The structural parameters and vibrational frequencies of HNCS and DNCS are taken from

Draper and Werner⁸. The values of force constants calculated by the method of Isotani by reducing to 10 different second order problems in the fifth order A' species are listed in Table 1 for both the molecules. It may be noted that the four values for each diagonal element F_{ii} are very close enough to justify the calculation of the mean value. The percentage of variation among the several values obtained for the same F_{ii} is very little. The interaction force constants (Table 1) show the usual trend of low values when compared with the diagonal force constants. The average values of F_{ii} are also listed with the final converged values of the solution set. The final converged values are also close to the approximate solution values justifying the approximation made earlier.

TABLE 1—SYMMETRISED FORCE CONSTANTS (mdyn/Å)
A' SPECIES OF HNCS AND DNCS

Molecule	F_{11}	F_{22}	F_{33}	F_{44}	F_{55}	F_{1j}	
HNCS	6.97	10.68	—	—	—	0.69	
	6.94	—	8.51	—	—	0.25	
	6.94	—	—	0.10	—	0.29	
	6.96	—	—	—	0.40	-0.31	
	—	10.62	8.63	—	—	-0.55	
	—	10.63	—	0.09	—	0.14	
	—	10.54	—	—	0.41	-0.49	
	—	—	8.37	0.09	—	0.07	
	—	—	8.29	—	0.98	-0.12	
	—	—	—	0.09	0.40	0.06	
	Mean values	6.96	10.62	8.44	0.09	0.40	—
	Final values	7.00	10.68	8.45	0.09	0.40	—
	DNCS	7.30	10.32	—	—	—	0.75
		7.28	—	8.78	—	—	0.13
7.28		—	—	0.10	—	0.21	
7.28		—	—	—	0.31	-0.14	
—		10.24	8.69	—	—	-0.57	
—		10.25	—	0.09	—	0.13	
—		10.16	—	—	0.33	-0.48	
—		—	8.40	0.09	—	0.05	
—		—	8.34	—	0.31	-0.14	
—		—	—	0.11	0.34	0.06	
Mean values		7.27	10.25	8.55	0.10	0.32	—
Final values		7.32	10.34	9.06	0.12	0.38	—

TABLE 2—VALENCE FORCE CONSTANTS (mydn/Å)*

	HNCS				DNCS			
	PW1	PW2	PW3	PW4	PW1	PW2	PW3	PW4
f_R	7.00	6.96	7.05	6.95	7.32	7.32	7.54	7.30
f_r	9.20	9.03	8.31	9.06	9.14	9.01	8.56	9.06
f_d	10.80	10.54	11.81	10.51	10.28	10.47	11.69	10.40
f_{α}	0.14	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.12
f_{ϕ}	0.37	0.42	0.45	0.42	0.38	0.35	0.40	0.35
f_{β}	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.49	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.42
f_{Rr}	0.66	0.43	0.42	0.36	0.62	0.80	1.68	0.70
f_{Ra}	-0.30	-0.04	0.40	0.03	-0.49	-0.06	0.62	0.06
$f_{R\alpha}$	0.29	0.01	0.10	0.01	0.21	0.01	0.21	0.01
$f_{R\phi}$	0.00	0.02	-0.33	-0.02	-0.14	-0.03	-0.38	-0.02
f_{rd}	-0.93	-0.94	-0.85	-0.94	-0.68	-0.64	-0.46	-0.64
f_{ra}	0.15	0.06	0.28	0.06	0.18	0.07	0.48	0.07
$f_{r\phi}$	-0.43	0.02	0.07	0.04	-0.03	0.02	0.14	0.05
$f_{d\alpha}$	-0.05	0.04	0.01	0.04	-0.05	0.05	0.06	0.05
$f_{d\phi}$	0.26	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.24	0.02	0.01	0.04
$f_{\alpha\phi}$	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.10	0.07

*PW1=Isotani's method, PW2=L-matrix approximation method, PW3=Herranz and Castano's method, PW4=kinetic constant method.

The valence force constants of HNCS and DNCS molecules are presented in Table 2. The H-N and D-N stretching force constants are same in this isotopically substituted pair of molecules, the C=S and C=N stretching force constants assume higher values compared with those of N-H stretching. The out-of-plane bending force constants f_s is low in both cases. Generally the diagonal force constants are almost the same for HNCS and its isotopically substituted derivative DNCS.

Three other methods (L-matrix approximation method, Herranz and Castano's method and kinetic constant method) have also been used to calculate the force constants of the molecules under consideration. The new procedure adopted here can be modified for any other method wherein off-diagonal elements F_{ij} are related with diagonal ones F_{ii} or F_{jj} . This idea is utilised in calculating the force constants by the method of kinetic constants.

The comparison of force constants obtained by the Isotani's method coupled with Newton-Raphson technique is made with those determined by using the other three methods mentioned in Table 2. Generally the values of force constants agree well with each other in all the methods and in particular the diagonal elements show good agreement. The off-diagonal elements are very low, particularly for those involving interaction among angle-bending coordinates.

References

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